

BPH and its predator population dynamics in field 5, Jiaying, Zhejiang, China. Insecticide applications: plot B, 21 Aug, triazophos; plot C, 25 Aug, a cartap-like insecticide + buprofezin.

insecticide used and the timing of an application, may cause BPH resurgence as a result of increased mortality of natural enemies.

An example of BPH resurgence is shown in the figure. The peak number of BPH eggs and nymphs + adults of generation 5 in plot B of field 5 were 1.5 times and twice as great as those in control plot A, respectively. While numbers of spiders and mirids in plot B were generally lower than those in plot A, the BPH-spider ratio was the highest (21.73) in the three plots. BPH and its major predators in plot C, after the first spray with buprofezin, were at the lowest level for the entire season. ■

Rice hull ash applied to seedbed reduces deadhearts in transplanted rice

A. S. Sawant and V. H. Patil, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth (KKV), Karjat 410201, Maharashtra, India, and N. K. Savant, International Fertilizer Development Center (IFDC), Muscle Shoals, Alabama 35662, USA

Silica (SiO_2) in rice plants can provide protection from stem borer infestation. Greenhouse experiments conducted in 1990-91 showed that SiO_2 content of rice seedlings (IR36) increased when black or gray rice hull ash (RHA) was applied to the seedbed. We conducted two field trials to investigate the effect of RHA applied to the seedbed on the deadheart incidence due to yellow stem borer (YSB) (*Scirpophaga incertulas*) and on grain yield at a RARS experimental farm during 1991 and 1992 wet seasons.

Blackish-gray RHA, amorphous according to x-ray diffraction analysis, was prepared by burning hulls in an open field. Raised beds, to which RHA at 0, 0.25, 1.0, and 2.0 kg/m^2 was incorporated

Effect of rice hull ash (RHA) applied to seedbed on SiO_2 content of seedlings, incidence of deadhearts, and grain yield of transplanted rice. The bars represent standard errors of the mean.

into the soil to a depth of 6-10 cm, were prepared before seeds of Jaya were sown. Nitrogen was applied @ 4.6 g N/m^2 in two splits as prilled urea (PU) or as PU amended with 5% Zn-EDTA to ensure an adequate supply of Zn.

For each treatment, 16 hills of five 4-wk-old rice seedlings/hill were trans-

planted in 0.8- × 0.8-m microplot using 20- × 20-cm spacing (25 hills/ m^2). The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with 10 treatments and 4 replicates in 1991 and 5 replicates in 1992. In 1991, 60 kg N/ha was split-applied as PU and 15 kg P/ha was basally applied as single superphosphate. Basally

deep-placed urea briquettes containing diammonium phosphate were used in 1992 to supply N and P at the same rates as in 1991.

The area surrounding the entire experimental plot was transplanted with Kolamba 540, a rice variety with high susceptibility to YSB. Artificial infestation was created by implanting one egg mass/four hills of Kolamba 540 at about 10 and 20 d after transplanting (DAT).

Total tillers and deadhearts were recorded at 30 DAT for the 16 hills in each plot. Data on percentage of deadhearts (using arcsin transformation) and yield were statistically analyzed. The 4-wk RHA-treated seedlings were

chemically analyzed for SiO₂ content.

Zn-EDTA had no effect on the SiO₂ content and percentage of deadhearts. The RHA-treated seedlings looked healthier and stronger, and they produced more biomass than did the untreated seedlings. Increased SiO₂ content of seedlings and decreased deadheart incidence in transplanted rice were observed with up to 1.0 kg RHA/m² (see figure). Yields seemed to be protected from losses due to the deadheart damage.

These findings have two practical implications. As an incentive to collect RHA for use in growing healthy rice seedlings, farmers could start using rice hull-fired stoves, such as the Vietnamese

Lò Trầu, for cooking. This would help reduce their firewood needs. The lower deadheart incidence can be achieved without using insecticide, thus helping to protect the environment.

At this stage, we do not have a satisfactory explanation as to why the yield increased when the SiO₂ content of the seedlings did not. One of our agronomic observations suggest that the RHA treatment improves plant vigor and, at times, increases the number of tillers/hill. This possible improvement in a yield-contributing factor may have increased grain yield. We will investigate this positive effect of RHA treatment on yield. ■

Prevalent insect pests of upland rice and some associated natural enemies in southeastern Nigeria

S. O. Emosarue and E. J. Usua, Crop Science Department and Biological Sciences Department, University of Calabar (UC), Calabar, Nigeria

Rice cultivation has increased dramatically in Nigeria since 1986 because of the government ban on rice imports.

Rodents, birds, and insects are major contributors to low yields in farmers' fields in southeastern Nigeria. We conducted this study during 1990 and 1991 early seasons (May-Aug) and late seasons (Sep-Dec) to provide information on prevalent insect pests and natural enemies in this rice agroecosystem.

The studies were conducted at the Teaching and Research Farm, Faculty of Agriculture, UC. ITA150 and ITA257, two popular early-maturing upland rice varieties developed by the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture were used. Each variety was planted in a 28.8 m² plot demarcated into four equal blocks of 7.2 m² and separated by a 1.75-m path. Four seeds of each variety were sown per hill at a spacing of 30 cm within rows and between rows. Plants were thinned to two per hill 20 d after sowing (DAS). A compound NPK fertilizer (15-15-15) was applied at 450 kg/ha in a split application, the first at 20 DAS and the second at booting.

Relative abundance of the 15 most common insect pests associated with upland rice varieties during early and late seasons in southeastern Nigeria.

Order Family Species	Relative abundance (%) as affected by planting date ^a			
	Early		Late	
	ITA150	ITA257	ITA150	ITA257
Coleoptera				
Chrysomelidae				
<i>Chaetocnema pulla</i>	49.6	62.3	30.3	29.7
<i>chapuis</i> (= <i>zeae</i> (Bryant))				
<i>Altica nigrita</i> (Lab.)	1.2	0.9	5.1	0.0
<i>Dactylispa</i> sp. nr. <i>paucispina</i> (Weise)	1.7	0.7	0.2	0.3
<i>Monolepta elegans</i> (Allard)	1.5	2.3	0.1	0.0
Coccinellidae				
<i>Chnootriba similis</i> (Mulsant)	10.4	5.1	4.9	4.4
Hemiptera				
Pyrrhocoridae				
<i>Dysdercus supertitiosus</i> (Fabricius)	0.2	0.0	32.3	26.9
Cicadellidae				
<i>Cofana spectra</i> (Distant)	16.0	10.6	11.9	12.0
<i>Nephotettix modulatus</i> (Mel.)	0.3	0.9	1.2	2.2
Pentatomidae				
<i>Aspavia armigera</i> (Fabricius)	5.7	8.3	10.3	15.0
Alydidae				
<i>Stenocoris claviformis</i> (Ahmad)	1.7	0.7	0.6	1.8
<i>Mirperus jaculus</i> (Thunbg.)	0.2	0.0	0.2	2.3
Aphrophoridae				
<i>Poophilus costalis</i> Walker	0.3	1.4	0.2	0.7
Coreidae				
<i>Cletus notatus</i> (Thunbg.)	0.7	1.2	0.1	0.0
Cercopidae				
<i>Locris erythromela</i> (Walker)	1.0	0.5	0.2	0.2
Diptera				
Diopsidae				
<i>Diopsis</i> spp.	4.0	4.2	2.2	4.5

^aRelative abundance (%) = $\frac{\text{Total no. of each species}}{\text{Total no. of prevalent species}} \times 100$

Total no. of prevalent spp. = total number of prevalent insect species collected from the vegetative stage to harvesting of the crop during the different cropping periods.